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USA Experience in the Field of Prevention of Domestic Violence and Animal Abuse

Стаття присвячена питанню досвіду США щодо попередження домашнього насильства та жорстокого поводження із тваринами. Розглянуто запровадження та діяльність у Штатах Теннессі Єдиного реєстру жорстокого поводження з тваринами, зростання маргінальної поведінки осіб від жорстокого поводження із тваринами до вбивств людей. МВС України частково почало розпізнавати взаємозв'язок жорстокого поводження із тваринами та домашнього насильства крізь призму оцінки ризику вчинення домашнього насильства.

Ключові слова: домашнє насильство, жорстоке поводження з тваринами, жорстоке поводження з дітьми, міжнародний досвід, реєстри правопорушень.

Статья посвящена вопросу опыта США по предупреждению домашнего насилия и жестокого обращения с животными. Рассмотрены внедрение и деятельность в Штатах Теннесси Единого реестра жестокого обращения с животными, рост маргинального поведения лиц от жестокого обращения с животными к убийствам людей. МВД Украины частично начало распознавать взаимосвязь жестокого обращения с животными и домашнего насилия через призму оценки риска совершения домашнего насилия.

Ключевые слова: домашнее насилие, жестокое обращение с животными, жестокое обращение с детьми, международный опыт, реестры правонарушений.

This article focuses on the experience of the United States in preventing domestic violence and animal abuse.

The article argues that animal abuse and domestic violence are interrelated phenomena, because they occur most often in the same homes. In families with domestic violence, animal abuse increases more often than in families where domestic violence occurs. The author elaborates on the relationship between domestic violence and animal cruelty, examines the psychological relationships and the interaction between the aggressor, the victim and the animal.

The experience of the United States, and in particular the state of Tennessee, is analysed separately. The types of registers to which they enter information on offenses that are directly or indirectly related to domestic violence, namely, the register: persons who have committed sexual offenses are examined; child abuse; ill-treatment of the elderly. Particular attention is paid to the implementation and activities in the State of Tennessee, especially the Tennessee Animal Abuse Registry.

Studies of serial teenage killers conducted by the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) have been analysed, which examined the development of criminal behaviour from animal abuse to the murder of human beings. The 'progression' in criminal behaviour of persons from animal abuse to murder is considered. In addressing these offenses, special attention is paid to the cruelty of animals as an important indicator not only of the existence of domestic violence, but also of the evidence of the offender's marginal tendencies, which may be realized in the future in killing people.

It is stated that in 2019 the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine has partially begun to recognize the relationship between animal abuse and domestic violence through the prism of assessing the risk of domestic violence. However, at the national level, this problem has not developed at all.

Keywords: domestic violence, animal abuse, child abuse, international experience, crime registries, US experience in combating domestic violence and animal abuse, identification of domestic violence.

Addressing the problem. The family is the smallest part of society, their totality is based on society. The family members are the closest people to whom each person counts on support and assistance. This is why the phenomenon of violence from one family member to another raises such concerns and a number of questions.

Analysis of research and publications. The issue of prevention and counteraction to domestic violence has become the subject of research by many scholars, namely: A.Baida, K.Levchenko, U.Novakovskaya A.Dominichak, E.Benkovska, L.Sukmanovska and others. Not only the legal aspects of domestic violence but also the psychological aspects have become the subject of scientific research. Through the prism of psychology, criminology, criminal law, the relationship between domestic violence and animal cruelty was investigated in the works of the following scientists: E. Alleyne, F. Akrow, B. Blonska, J. Zorza, M. Zinley, N. Taylor, A. Fitzgerald, S. Parfitt and others.

Previously unsolved problems. However, due to the high latency of domestic violence, there are many psychological, social aspects of this phenomenon, cultural differences in the understanding of human and animal places in society, differences in the effectiveness of police response in different countries to domestic violence, animal abuse, there are several aspects that need further investigation. The above determines the relevance of the chosen topic.

Main body.

In recent years, there has been an increase in attention to the phenomenon of animal abuse [1, p.402]. Researchers say that animal abuse and domestic violence (or, very often, some scientists use the term partner violence) are interrelated, because they occur most often in the same homes. In the family where there is domestic violence, animal abuse appears more often than in families without domestic violence [2, p.41]. The links between animal cruelty, child abuse and domestic violence are complex [3, p.399]. It should also be noted that various forms of domestic violence tend to coexist or cluster. Thus, in the case of violence between parents (close relatives, foster parents), they do not fulfil their responsibilities for the upbringing of children, and also abuse the latter [2, p.41].

Of particular note is the experience of the public authorities of Tennessee (USA). For example,

in 2015, the Tennessee Regulators adopted the Law on the Tennessee according to which the Tennessee Animal Abuse Registry was first introduced. The designated registry began operation on January 1, 2016. It is an online database of offenders who have been convicted of animal cruelty. The Tennessee Bureau of Investigation contains information about the offender's identity, including his last name, middle name, and photo. If the person was convicted for the first time, his / her data is stored in the register for 2 years, if the person is convicted repeatedly, then for 5 years. Legislators, when deciding to establish a single registry for animal cruelty, were motivated by a desire to "oppose animal cruelty", but later realized that such a registry also prevented violence against humans [4, p.360]. Zoo advocates are convinced that the existence of such a base in itself acts as a deterrent to those who wish to commit acts of animal cruelty [5]. In the US there are also such registers as:

- National Register of Sexual Offenders;
- Register of persons who committed sexual crimes;
- National Register of Child Abuse;
- National Register of Child Abuse;
- National Register of Elderly Abuse;
- Register of elderly abuse;
- other registers of persons and offenses [6, p.209]

Analyzing the above registers in the USA, it is possible to draw some intermediate conclusions.

First, the link between domestic violence and animal cruelty is determined not only in theory but also in practice. That is why the lawmaker of Tennessee to assist in the fight against these offenses in every way contributes and practically helps law enforcement agencies in this direction. A single register of animal cruelty allows not only the rapid monitoring of the recurrence of these offenses, but also the prevention of new offenses in the field of zoological protection.

Secondly, it is extremely important that public authorities pay particular attention to the most vulnerable categories of persons, namely children and the elderly.

Thirdly, it is absolutely true that recognizing and countering at the national level the problem of animal cruelty helps prevent animal and human abuse in the future.

In itself, animal cruelty is characterized by high latency. The criminal who commits animal abuse is more dangerous to family members than to

other people. Because these aggressors have strong behavioural control over the victim, inherent sexual abuse, marital rape, psychological abuse, and harassment. Researchers have identified the most important indicators that can indicate the occurrence of domestic violence, namely:

- easy access to firearms;
- the presence in the person's behavior of the threat of suicide or murder;
- animal abuse or threat [7, p.50].

US researchers insist that animal cruelty is a form of rehearsal of violence against humans. This should be taken as a serious problem and in no case ignored. According to US scientists, if these animal behaviours are not recognized as a problem and not corrected and / or treated, it will grow into greater proportions and more serious consequences. These aggressive actions by children against animals may be an early diagnostic indicator of future psychopathology. For example, a study by serial federal teenage killers conducted by the Federal Bureau of Investigation in 1988 found the following:

Most of the murderers analysed at the time of childhood committed cruel forms of animal abuse. For example, in his youth, Jeffrey Damer (a serial killer), strung up the skulls of dogs he had killed with sticks, and hung them in the back yard. Scientists have studied the stories of 28 sex offenders and murders, and found the following:

- 36% had committed the most severe forms of animal abuse in childhood;
- and 46% - in adolescence [2, p.42].

It should be noted that individual scientists are considering factors that influence the likelihood of animal abuse in people of all ages, based on their own negative experiences.

Scientists say that the likelihood of adult abuse is increased when, in childhood, parents used threats (such as harming a pet) against an animal or taking away pets as a method of discipline. It should be noted that the likelihood of abuse caused by a negative family environment in childhood is higher in men than in women.

Absence of human concern (moral attitude), solely consumer attitude towards animals, dominant attitude towards animals (e.g. beliefs that one can control, dominate animals) are directly related and increase the likelihood (likelihood) of animal cruelty [8, p .351].

Note that when assessing the risk of domestic violence in Ukraine, the National Police of Ukraine calculate the likelihood of continuation or re-commission of a specified offense, the grave consequences of its commission, including the death of the victim. The specified process is carried out by establishing and analysing information on a specific offense.

For example, among other factors, it increases the risk of domestic violence threatening to kill or have already committed murder, deliberately harming a pet and / or other animal. This is envisaged in the provisions of Order 369/180 of March 13, 2019 of the Ministry of Social Policy of Ukraine and the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine "On Approval of the Procedure for Conducting a Risk Assessment of Domestic Violence" [9]. *So, we can point out that since 2019 the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine has begun to recognize the relationship between animal abuse and domestic violence. However, the issues have not been sufficiently researched and have not been reflected in the Concept of the State Social Program for Preventing and Combating Domestic and Gender-Based Violence for the Period up to 2023 [10]. Accordingly, as of July 2019, Ukraine has not yet implemented the Unified State Register of Cases of Domestic and Gender-Based Violence, which has been in force for over a year according to current legislation. Unfortunately, the importance of introducing a single state register of cases of animal abuse is not discussed at all.*

Thus, animal abuse and domestic violence are interrelated phenomena with high latency. The review and analysis of identified phenomena, the development of prevention and counteraction strategies by law enforcement agencies should be integrated with a multidisciplinary approach. That is why the implementation of not only the Unified State Register of Cases of Domestic and Gender-Based Violence, but also the Unified State Register of Cases of Cruelty to Animals would contribute not only to the prevention and counteraction of these offenses, but also to the better provision of police services by law enforcement officers in Ukraine.

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